

Open Schooling: transforming the school curriculum through science education

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Silvar Ferreira Ribeiro - State University of Bahia – UNEB

Address – Rua Le Champ 229 – Torre 11 – Ap 603 – Patamares – Salvador Bahia – Brazil – CEP 41.680-090

Sonia Maria da Conceição Pinto - State University of Bahia – UNEB

Address – Rua Le Champ 229 – Torre 11 – Ap 603 – Patamares – Salvador Bahia – Brazil – CEP 41.680-090

Ana Karine Loula Torres Rocha - State University of Bahia – UNEB

Address - Rua Domicio Marques Dourado, 98, Bairro Asa Sul - Irecê / Bahia / Brazil - CEP: 44.900-000

sfribeiro@uneb.br, spinto@uneb.br, aklrrocha@uneb.br

Abstract.

This article describes a project developed in Bahia during the last three years that involves basic educational schools, students and their families, teachers, policy makers, enterprises and scientists from universities. This project, called Connect, benefited almost two thousand students in Bahia – Brazil with more than 30% of them completing scientific action reports using the Care-Know-Do methodology. Open schooling, with a focus on science education, has allowed students to access a wide range of scientific knowledge and engage in practical experiences and real-world challenges. The open schooling approach has not been limited to traditional classrooms, giving students the freedom to explore topics of interest and collaborate with peers. The schools involved in the project addressed different topics, with a strong connection to global sustainability issues. The project also promoted closer ties between universities and schools, involving researchers and scientists in basic education activities. Furthermore, families got involved in the activities, and the participation of the local political class was notable, suggesting the possibility of integrating the principles of open schooling and responsible research and innovation into public educational policies in these municipalities.

1. Introduction

This article portrays the conception, development and results of an international educational action that involved five countries in Europe and Latin America, lasted three years and reached significant numbers of participants. This is an initiative built with the participation of universities, government and private institutions that designed a project called CONNECT - including open schooling with engaging future-oriented science, submitting it to a call for the Horizon 2020 Program - Science with and for Society

(SwafS), funded by the European Commission and implemented between the years 2020 to 2023. The International Consortium that involved the Open University and Mastery Science - United Kingdom, the Universitatea Valahia Târgoviște - Romania, The Living Lab for Health at IrsiCaixa - Spain, the State University of Bahia and the Pontifical Catholic University of Paraná - Brazil, the Regional Education Directorate of Crete - Greece, GLOBAZ, S.A. - LOBA - Portugal, EXUS SOFTWARE MONOPROSOPI ETAIRIA PERIORISMENIS EVTHINIS - Greece and FONDEN TEKNOLOGIRADET - Denmark. Together and with well-defined roles, all these participating institutions worked to ensure that the established objectives were achieved, the goals were achieved, and the educational, management and evaluation methodologies were implemented.

In 2023, in global numbers in the last year of its completion, according to Okada et. al. (2023), the Connect Project has already benefited more than 30 thousand students, distributed in Brazil (9,349), Greece (3,752), Romania (2,140). in the United Kingdom (910) and Spain (585), countries where activities were carried out in public and private schools. A percentage of more than 40% of these students completed their scientific action reports in line with the Kare-Know-Do methodology, developed and implemented by Connect, applying the open schooling approach and demonstrating the connections established between science and their real life.

This overview presented above had the purpose of presenting the global dimension of the Connect Project, however, the data that will be explored in this section discussed in this article will be focused on the Brazilian experience and more specifically on the project actions developed in Bahia, through the State University of Bahia - UNEB, member of the Consortium, one of the institutions executing the project with schools, as other institutions in the consortium performed management, dissemination, advisory and evaluation functions.

The Connect Project methodology was developed, shared and implemented by all participants and will be described in this article, and this text presents the results achieved in the Bahian cities that were part of it.

2. The principles of the Connect Project

Some fundamental principles were established for the project, including increasing the scientific capital of young people, basic education students, with the aim of awakening interest in science and, consequently, in a scientific career. According to Riley (2005), young people often find science interesting, but do not consider themselves likely to be future scientists, because they lack cultural familiarity with science, they also lack confidence that they can achieve this goal, as well as role models, such as proximity to scientists. Basic education students also lack the opportunity to talk about science outside of school, with their families. “There is evidence that young people with greater scientific capital are more likely to want to stay with science after school” (Riley, 2005). According to the author, a possible solution to awaken young people's interest in science and a scientific career is to make the school open and establish continuous external partnerships with science professionals and families, carrying out projects with university researchers and industry professionals, offering provide them with more authentic contexts to develop skills and knowledge about science and its application.

Aiming to act to transform this reality, it sought to apply a model known as open schooling, with the aim of expanding students' scientific capital, through an inclusive, sustainable curriculum, with participatory scientific action as its main focus, involving families, universities and companies to promote the attitude “science is for me, in life, now and in the future”.

Open schooling, the model chosen for Connect's educational activities, adopted scientific action in the basic education curriculum as the basis of its proposal, presenting challenges for young people to reflect on the survival of planet Earth, sustainable life, teaching them the concept of assessing the life cycle of the products we consume, their environmental impact during manufacturing, use and disposal. This approach to scientific education, brought by Project Connect based on the concept of open schooling, is consistent with what in Brazil we call CTSA education, an acronym for Science, Technology, Society and Environment, which according to Conrado, Nunes-Neto (2019) is practiced and much debated in the field of science teaching, which is referenced in academic research, public

policies and education oriented towards the relationships between science, technology and society. According to Pinto, et. al (2018), in studies on scientific arguments by basic education students, come to the conclusion that young people, despite having good arguments, have many difficulties in developing scientific arguments, even with the guidance of their teachers.

To put open schooling into practice through scientific action in the formal curriculum, five phases were structured: 1. Define the challenge, 2. raise awareness, 3. research and learn knowledge, 4. prepare the scientific action and 5. carry out the action in practice. These five steps are structured in a methodology called the Care-Know-Do framework, a practical structure to integrate formal and informal learning, involving scientific action.

Phase 1, We-Care involves a sensitive and accurate look at the reality around them, also dialogue with families and professionals from universities and companies to identify socio-scientific dilemmas by students with the help and guidance of teachers, leading to elaboration of a scientific question that will represent the challenge to be faced.

In phase 2. WE-Know, students seek formal learning of scientific content that will support them in understanding scientific knowledge on the issue raised, using books, articles in scientific databases, dialogues and lectures with experts from the companies and scientists from universities, always looking for answers and solutions.

Finally, phase 3, We-Do, in which students transform their knowledge and skills into participatory science-action, proposing solutions to the challenges defined in the initial stages.

In addition to the concept of scientific capital and the open schooling model, the Connect Project was based on another important scientific approach, known as responsible research and innovation (RRI), the acronym in English for Responsible, Research And Innovation, understood as an approach that involves researchers, citizens, politicians, companies and organizations to collaborate in research and innovation processes with a focus on responsibility both in the process and in the results, according to the needs and expectations of society (BARDONE; LIND, 2016; COMMISSION, 2013; OKADA, 2008; VON SCHOMBERG, 2013).

3. The principles of the Connect Project

Located in the northeast region of Brazil, Bahia is one of the twenty-seven federative units, with an estimated population in 2021 of approximately 15 million inhabitants and a total area of 564,733 km². Its capital Salvador was the first seat of the Brazilian government in 1549, by the Portuguese who arrived here in the year 1500 and governed until 1823, when Brazil's independence was consolidated, right here in Bahia, from where the last Portuguese troops were expelled.

The Connect Project's scientific education actions in Bahia began in the first year of its implementation and benefited fourteen schools, involving five municipalities, sixty-six teachers and two thousand, seven hundred and thirteen students.

The territorial scope of the project, as can be seen in the map below, figure 1, contained it in the municipalities of Araci, 222 kilometers from the capital Salvador, Camaçari, 48 km, Candeias 50 km, Irecê 485 km, LAPÃO – 477 km, Presidente Dutra - 495 km and Senhor do Bonfim - 384 km.

Figure 1 - Map of Bahia

In these locations, schools were initially visited to be invited to join the project, they participated in the initial meetings to present the scientific, pedagogical and methodological principles, in addition to the curricular approach of open schooling and responsible research and innovation. In 2021, Year 1 of the Connect Project, two schools, one in the municipality of Irecê and the other in Camaçari, joined the project, with the others choosing to participate in the second and third years, 2022 and 2023.

The projects developed in Bahia can be seen in the table below, figure 2 - Connect number in 2022, which presents the project status in December 2022, knowing that the actions continued and new data will be added in the final report, including the year 2023, as activities to bring together other schools in different cities have continued and are under development.

Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7
			NUMEROS DO CONNECT EM 2022			
Item	Cidade	Escola	Nome do Projeto	Professores	Participantes	Concluintes
1	Bonfim	CESB	Índice de Área Verde-(IAV)- Bairro e Meio ambiente e saúde – as arbovíroses	6	97	60
2	Irece	ACM	SUSTENTABILIDADE AMBIENTAL E ENERGIA RENOVÁVEL	5	400	200
3	Irece	ACM	SUSTENTABILIDADE NO COTIDIANO	4	400	200
4	Camaçari	CETEP-RM	Projeto MECADROID - Robótica na Escola com Material Reutilizáveis	1	5	5
5	Camaçari	CETEP-RM	Democratização da Educação Científica e Tecnológica na Escola	2	65	45
6	Lapão	Tiradentes	Meio ambiente: Sustentabilidade e qualidade de vida	2	112	112
7	Lapão	Gaspar	Consciência, cidadania e sustentabilidade	6	284	284
8	Lapão	Valentina	Projeto Plantando o Futuro Valentina Matos	7	221	221
9	Camaçari	CETEP-RM	PROJETO OLIVA - PRAIA SUSTENTÁVEL	2	7	3
10	P. Dutra	Valter Barreto	MEIO AMBIENTE: PRESERVAÇÃO E SUSTENTABILIDADE	3	200	200
11	Lapão	Honorato	MEIO AMBIENTE: PRESERVAÇÃO E SUSTENTABILIDADE	18	234	234
12	Lapão	Deraldo	VAMOS PLANTAR HOJE A SEMENTE DO AMANHÃ	4	150	150
13	Lapão	M. DOURADO	ESCOLA SUSTENTÁVEL, COMUNIDADE SAUVADEL	3	170	170
14	Lapão	Elzita Vieira	PROJETO CAATINGA NÃO É DESERTO	3	368	92
Total				66	2713	1976

Figure 2 - Connect Project Board in Bahia

We can see, in the table above, the acronyms of the schools' names, the city where they are located, the number of teachers and students who participated and completed the project's scientific actions, as well as their titles.

In the city of Senhor do Bonfim, which is located 384 kilometers from the capital Salvador, a municipality with eighty thousand inhabitants and a strong cultural tradition, with the June festivals being the best known and sought after by tourists and residents of the city and surrounding areas, CESB - Senhor do Bonfim Educational Center, developed the Green Area Index Project (IAV) - Neighbourhood, Environment and Health - tree viruses. In this scientific action, students took measurements of the city's green areas and carried out calculations to compare with international standards. The results summarize the statement of a student: "Before I thought that the 'things' I studied at school were only useful for school... now I think differently". We can infer that this statement from a young man denotes his change in attitude and understanding of the meaning of school education. It demonstrates that the knowledge constructed will be useful in your life and not just at school.

In addition to this project, registered on the Connect Platform, scientific education through open schooling led to other actions at CESB. Scientific actions were carried out through several other projects developed by students based on their interests, highlighting Physics, "Movement Study", Accessibility at School was researched, with a movement simulator, experiencing in practice the use of ramps by disabled people, presenting improvement proposals to the school management; on "numbers and mathematical functions", the Unified Health System (SUS) was investigated, with a survey on the topic "Aedes in Focus", involving 89 (eighty-nine) people from the community who answered a questionnaire about the importance of the SUS . The action was a public awareness campaign. Also, in health, it dealt with Teenage Pregnancy, involving families, the community and companies in a "Health Fair", Sexual Education and Pregnancy Prevention. In the area of environment and sustainability, combating wild animal trafficking with teaching zoology and environmental education in schools, with scientists in the field of biology "Vertebrates and Conservation".

In the municipality of Irecê, 485 kilometers from the capital, the Antônio Carlos Magalhães Municipal School (ACM). This school was a pioneer in the region and began its work with the Bird Rewilding Project of the Semiarid Northeast of Brazil.

Figure 3 - Public campaign to free the birds

The rewilding project consisted of the analysis of the Phyto physiognomy of the caatinga in urban spaces, a practical study, identification of caged birds in the city of Irecê, exhibition of the study carried out at the event open to the community, entitled Knowledge Fair, awareness campaign on the topic covered in a public square in the neighbourhood where the school is located.

In the second year, having chosen the global theme Zero Carbon, through the Sustainability in Everyday Life Project, the school involved students and teachers of basic education in the areas of Natural Sciences, Human Sciences, Agroecology and Environmental Sciences, Wind Energy Generation, with the participation of researchers specializing in Rural Education. The Project was carried out in three stages, following the Care-Know-Do methodology. In the “CARE” Stage, a Based on reflections in the classroom and dialogues with families, 8th and 9th grade students realized the need for changes in consumption and eating habits to preserve life on the planet.

After a live broadcast with experts and scientists, many discussions in the classroom, two socio-scientific dilemmas were prioritized: materials that are inappropriately discarded in nature, causing pollution and the issue of the use of pesticides on vegetables, a very common practice in the region. In the KNOW” Stage, The students researched the impact that inadequate plastic disposal causes on the environment, learned about plastic islands in the oceans and identified that these large global impacts are caused by small local actions. They also carried out studies regarding the impacts caused by the use of pesticides, both the impacts on the environment and people's health, they acquired knowledge about ways of growing vegetables without the use of pesticides and how to produce natural fertilizers from composting.

Figure 4 - Organic Planting at School

In the DO Stage: the students three actions: 1. PLASTIC MATERIALS COLLECTION CAMPAIGN – The class teacher got in touch with a group that collects recyclable materials, the students carried out a campaign to collect these materials with other classes at the school and with their family members; The material collected was sold and the amount raised was used in a tour with all participants as a form of incentive and prize. 2. SUSTAINABLE CLEANING CAMPAIGN – Upon learning of the damage caused by the inappropriate disposal of multi-purpose sponges, made from synthetic and non-biodegradable material, the students promoted a campaign to replace these sponges with natural biodegradable materials, presenting these options even to canteen employees. 3. ORGANIC GARDEN AT SCHOOL – The students built a vegetable garden in the school nursery, (figure 3, above) chose the vegetables and carried out the entire process: soil preparation, fertilization with organic compounds,

planting, monitored the growth of the vegetables, harvested and delivered to the school canteen to supplement the lunch.

In the municipality of Lapão, 477 kilometers from Salvador, adherence to the Connect Project was organized by the Department of Education with the involvement of seven schools in the municipal network, generating a large movement of transformation of curricular practices with the involvement of a large number of teachers, students, families and rulers. The Tiradentes, Elzita Vieira, Antonia Gaspar, Honorato Gaspar de Souza, Deraldo José de Souza, Manoel Dourado and Valentina Matos schools, all of basic education, coordinated projects, which took as their central theme the global challenge of Carbon Neutral and carried out projects aimed at the environment, sustainability, quality of life, citizenship, nature preservation and planting seedlings and seeds on the outskirts of the city.

Activities related to the curriculum were carried out and proved to be extremely important, relevant and challenging, as they were carried out in the post-pandemic period, which determined social isolation for a long time, but the active participation of the entire school community and local society, resulted in representative work from the beginning of the preparation, the elaboration of the project and its culmination in the Children and Youth Conference, held in the municipality. Open Schooling proved to be very challenging and useful for teachers, students, staff and school leaders, because the project was carried out in an interdisciplinary way involving all disciplines and members of the community. The results were evidenced by the active participation of students from the elaboration of projects to the production of materials until the final result. Student Ruan Afrisio mentioned in his speech about Connect's actions that “We must become aware that we need the environment to be looked after and preserved to live healthier”.

Figure 5 - The various stages and actions of Connect in Lapão

In Lapão, the steps of the Care-Know-Do methodology were also followed and the activities were carried out in three major stages: In the first, “CARE”: students were challenged to critically observe real-life problems that affect their community, talk to their classmates, family and teachers to understand the need to take care of the environment around them and analyse residents' actions aimed at preservation of the Environment and the surroundings of Lagoas and Canões.

Early Childhood Education and Elementary Education I and II students, aged between 3 and 15 years old, participated in the activities. In the KNOW” stage, students researched topics related to environmental preservation, used knowledge about environmental preservation and sustainability, developed practices to take care of the place where we live, value the importance of collective work, scientific research and forms of production without aggression against nature.

In the DO step: the students prepared various texts, read, prepared pamphlets and posters, participated in lectures and the Children's Conference, planted several seedlings, distributed them to the

community with the support of the Secretariat of Environment and Agriculture. They participated and completed collective and individual activities and were supported by families and community members.

In the city of Presidente Dutra, also in the Irecê Identity Territory, a municipality 495 kilometers away from Salvador, the project developed was Environment: Preservation and Sustainability, an initiative based on the principles of Open Schooling about caring for the place where we live. Managers, teachers and basic education students participated, as well as other professionals from the Valter Barreto Municipal School. The activities included science professionals and were supported by the State University of Bahia (UNEB). The purpose of the project is to support scientific education in basic education, especially for the inclusion of students in situations of social disadvantage, increasing their scientific capital and awakening interest in science. The three stages of Connect - Care-Know-Do, which translate into an initial awareness-raising activity (care) about real socio-scientific problems, then research to know and propose scientific actions based on facts and data and the third stage of acting that means to do something in search of a solution to the problem studied.

In the “CARE” Stage: students were challenged to observe their community, both the place where they live, the school and its surroundings, aiming to identify problems that affect life in society (socio-scientific dilemmas) and that are relevant to be studied in search of solutions. The real-life problem that they decided was most important for this study, after debate and prioritization among everyone brought to the project meetings, was the lack of care and preservation of the surroundings of the lagoon and dam in the city center. The students who participated in the activities were in the 6th to 9th year of Elementary School, aged between 11 and 15 years old.

In the KNOW” Stage: students researched knowledge about the preservation of waters, life and the preservation of aquatic species and their importance for the environment, built at this stage through research, participation in lectures, readings and classes on the topic, which dealt with the preservation of the environment. There was a debate on the development of sustainable practices to take care of the place where we live, realizing the importance of collective work, mutual respect, knowledge of environmental practices to take care of the environment, various research on the topic and others.

Figure 6 - Lagoon protection activity in Presidente Dutra

In the DO Stage: In the end, the students prepared different texts, different readings, posters, banners, participated in walks and lectures, planted seedlings, distributed different seedlings to the community with support from the Departments of Environment, Education and Agriculture, and others. They completed the activities in groups in partnership with families and community members.

In the municipalities of Camaçari and Candeias, both in the Metropolitan Region of Salvador with an average distance of 50 kilometres from the capital, several projects were carried out following the principles of open schooling and the Connect methodology. The Territorial Center for Professional Education - CETEP-RM is headquartered in both cities and its units worked together, bringing together

teachers and students in carrying out projects. This vocational high school joined Connect from the first year of its implementation and added to its scientific education experience, which was already quite significant, including the organization of an Annual Scientific Fair, called FECITESC, in which students exhibit of the work developed throughout the academic year and is evaluated by external examiners, receiving awards and certificates recognizing their performance.

Adding the principles of the Connect Project, students identified problems and sought solutions, supported by scientific research, promoting confidence and aspiration to pursue scientific careers, through practices based on socio-scientific dilemmas, with the guidance of professors and guest scientists, to discuss real problems. The research activities with the students materialized in projects such as educational robotics with recyclable materials, science teaching in basic education, public lighting, manufacturing of lamps from reused palm oil, public security and lighting, manufacturing of biodegradable plastics from microalgae, financial education, sustainable beaches and bioplastics from cassava remains from the city's street market. These projects stood out as important actions developed based on real problems, translated as socio-scientific dilemmas and studied under the methodological guidelines of the Connect Project.

The SUSTAINABLE BEACH Project was an exploratory research, with active interventions on beaches in Camaçari-Bahia, aiming to raise environmental awareness among the local community and tourists. The field study, using questionnaires and collecting seawater samples, images and waste found, found that the beaches were suitable for bathing, without coliforms, but there were no garbage collectors in the sand, only on the sidewalk. A letter to the local city hall requested environmental impact actions.

Figure 7 - Sustainable Beach Project Activity

The FEIRA RAÍZ Project focused on the adequate disposal of organic cassava waste, which contains a significant amount of starch, generated at the Camaçari open-air market, enabling the production of bioplastic through polymerization. In the environment, organic materials degrade spontaneously and recycle nutrients in processes such as the carbon and nitrogen cycles, but when disposed of inappropriately, they can cause serious risks to the environment, the health of the soil, water, air, exposing the population and animals to toxic and pathogenic substances and generate waste of raw materials.

Figure 8 - Feira Raiz Project Activity

The work provided an opportunity to spread knowledge about the responsible disposal of waste, contributing to the general well-being of the environment. The evaluation instrument was answered by 27 CETEP students, seeking to obtain opinions about science and their participation in the project. Regarding science being useful for life, 89% agreed and 12% said they were unsure, highlighting the need to carry out actions to develop and strengthen experiences that stimulate critical reflective thinking and promote the scientific capital of young people at school. Regarding the best experiences with participating in the project, a student's statement caught our attention: "step by step on how it starts, how it produces, how members should be guided and how to play a good role as a leader", highlighting the phases of preparation and implementation of the CONNECT project, and the "CARE-KNOW-DO" methodology.

In another statement about learning science, the student said that "unfortunately it is a little publicized area, I believe that if we could promote more, there would be more people in the area, as it is an exciting activity for the brain, opening the eyes to the world, demonstrating interest in science". In other words, students are empowered with knowledge, skills, attitudes and values as subjects who can transform their lives, the environment and their communities through challenges that are relevant to them (CARE), knowledge learned, researched, discussed (KNOW) and transformative actions (DO). Finally, there was a great involvement of teachers, students, families and communities with the proposed themes, highlighting the importance of open schooling and science education, as key elements for greater social and environmental awareness.

4. Conclusion

It was observed that the open schooling approach with a focus on scientific education deepens scientific knowledge in different areas, among young people in basic education, through interdisciplinary activities. Not only does it allow students to access a wide variety of scientific knowledge, but it also engages them in practical experiences and real-world challenges. In open schooling, science teaching is not restricted to traditional classrooms. Students have the freedom to explore topics of interest and dive into projects that involve scientific investigations. They can collaborate with colleagues, use online resources, and actively participate in building their own knowledge.

Attention was drawn to the variety of themes chosen by the schools, as well as the connection of these themes with global themes of the planet's sustainability. It can be seen in the description of the projects that the issue of life on land and water, the production of clean energy, protection of natural

resources, cleaning of the oceans, assessment of green areas in urban locations, combating the irregular disposal of plastics and other waste, organic platinum, protection of animals and habitat, among others. It is also worth highlighting the close relationship between the chosen themes and socio-environmental issues and local socio-scientific dilemmas, around the school, in the communities where the students live and even in the management practices of the school space itself.

Many Connect Project actions caused positive impacts in the different realities where it took place. We can highlight, in addition to the learning and changes that took place at school, its pedagogical practices that are renewed, the approach to the university, the participation of several researchers, scientists in basic education activities, going to give lectures or even participating in stages of presentations and evaluations of project results.

It is also worth highlighting the involvement of families who were present in activities, science fairs, fieldwork and certifications and recognition of the work carried out by students.

The participation of the political class stood out in the Bahia experience. Mayors, education secretaries and their advisors, deputy mayors, councilors were involved with Connect's scientific actions. Certainly, the principles of open schooling and responsible research and innovation have the possibility of integrating public educational policies in these municipalities that participated in Connect and the university will monitor this. There are already invitations to present the Project at pedagogical meetings in some municipalities and we will be contributing in this way to influence municipal education plans.

The statistics generated by the application of questionnaires answered by students, unfortunately in smaller numbers, only 728 (seven hundred and twenty-eight), 26.83% of the 2713 (two thousand seven hundred and thirteen) effective number of participants, motivated by the difficulty of accessing Electronic devices, such as computers, tablets and cell phones connected to the Internet, still provide data that can reveal how much of these changes reported above actually occurred. The age group between 11 and 16 years old predominated with 90% of the participants, with fourteen years old being the largest of them with 29.67%. Regarding gender, 53% were women and 46% were men. The comments recorded by these students in their responses 56% of them agree that science will be useful in their lives, 43% declare that they feel confident in using the scientific approach to formulate questions and ideas about real socio-scientific dilemmas. It is also noteworthy that 41% are confident in their scientific knowledge, 39% say they know how to justify their point of view using scientific arguments, 46% say they are confident in doing/participating in scientific projects, 37% in talking about science and 56% said that learning science is fun, 36% said they would like to work as a scientist and 34% would like to be seen as an expert in science. All this data in greater detail is published in the Connect Bahia Brazil report, on the Student report link, available at [CONNECT - Google My Maps](#).

In the open answers, one of the students stands out who stated: "I learned that it is necessary to analyse and research to reach a conclusion, but that sometimes we do not reach an exact answer". Among other statements representative of Connect's actions, we note that this is very emblematic, as it reveals the development of true scientific spirit, of incessant search for answers, but of the benefit of the doubt as a scientific attitude, summarizing well that scientific actions brought good results in changing attitude towards increasing the scientific capital of these young people.

In the same link you can read the teachers' responses and the global report from Bahia, which provide revealing data on how important this project was, not only for the students, but for the teachers as well and for the schools.

Finally, we can say from our position as the Project coordination team in Bahia that we followed every action, every planning, the uncertainties and difficulties that arose along the way, the creative ways of overcoming them, that the Connect Project made an impact on local education. where it happened and leaves a great potential, as its effects will not end with the conclusion of the three-year period already established in its schedule, but will continue, in the lives of students and teachers, as well as in schools. The same can be said for universities, as we have made commitments to continue our actions with schools, and we even have another project approved by a Brazilian research body, involving a network of seven universities, including UNEB and PUC-PR, which aims, together with five other

Brazilian universities, to implement projects with an approach to open schooling, responsible research and innovation and scientific education.

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